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INTEGRATION OF DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to considering importance of fostering discourse analysis in English language classroom. In order to achieve the most important goal of teaching foreign languages, which is to develop secondary linguistic personalities capable of full communication in the target language, tasks that aim to develop communicative and discursive competencies are becoming increasingly relevant. These skills become particularly important when it comes to the training of future philologists and translators through the usage of textual materials.

Keywords: *language learning, communication, discourse analysis, discourse theory, discursive psychology, critical discourse analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Recent findings indicate that the theory of text, also known as the “theory of discourse” in European science, emerged as a scientific discipline in the second half of the 20th century at the intersection of several sciences, including hermeneutics, sociology, pragmatics, semiotics, linguistics, informatics, rhetoric, and psychology. It has a complete individual ontological character and encompasses any sequence of signs, irrespective of the quantity of transdisciplinary crossings. It is noteworthy that since a vocal text is its primary object, the information gathered in linguistics throughout the process of characterizing and describing the text is significant in this context. Learning how language is employed in various texts and circumstances, or in texts that define or even support conversation, is the process of conducting discourse analysis. During the 1970s, discourse analysis gained popularity in academic circles. “The use of language in fluent discourse, going on over a series of sentences and featuring the interaction of the speaker (writer) and auditor (reader) in a particular context of the situation and within the framework of specific social and cultural conventions” is the definition of this term provided by Abrams and Harfam in the Glossary of Literary Terms. Discourse analysis, as contrast to grammatical analysis,

which concentrates on a single sentence, examines the widespread and everyday use of language both inside and between certain social groups. Furthermore, although discourse analysis depends on the speech (oral and written) outcomes of many people`s works in order to determine the common language uses, grammar experts typically create their own cases that are then examined.

METHODS

A discourse analysis in the context of institutional practices that have marked out text divisions and established literature as the subject of particular enshrinements is made possible by the concepts and methods of contemporary discourse study. “Discourse” has been a term for at least a decade now. It is commonly employed freely and without definition in scientific writings and discussions. This idea has become so unclear that it either means very little at all or has varied meanings depending on the context in which it is used. The idea that language is structured according to distinct patterns that people`s utterances follow when they participate in different areas of social life, such as “political discourse” and “medical discourse”, however, is frequently the base assumption behind the word “discourse”. Examining these patterns is called discourse analysis. However, there is little clarity in this description of discourses that comes from common sense regarding their nature, functions, and analysis techniques. Searching for more advanced discourse analysis theories and techniques is necessary in this case. Discourse analysis is simply one of several interdisciplinary methodologies that may be used to investigate a wide range of social domains in a wide range of study categories, as one rapidly discovers while conducting their search. Furthermore, there is not a whole lot of agreement on the definition or analysis of discourses. A variety of viewpoints make their own recommendations and, in a way, try to claim the terms “discourse” and “discourse analysis” for their own meanings. But, by offering the provisional definition of a discourse as a specific manner of discussing and comprehending world (or a portion of it). According to G. Brown and G. Yul [2, p. 24], the subject of study in “discourse analysis” is rarely established based solely on a single line (or even a single text). The discourse analysis researchers should first gather the necessary quantity of data in our example text units for their observations. Next, look for phenomena in handwriting or audio recordings, such as the unique characteristics of each text, its resemblance to other texts, its non-standard forms in the text under study, and how they relate to the semantic load. Put simply, this means that while grammar analysis focuses solely on sentence structure, word choice, and stylistic decisions at the sentence level, many of which take into account cultural factors, discourse analysis examines spoken, real-world, and cultural language use. but not the conversation`s human component. Text and discourse are treated as nearly synonymous by Michael Stubbs (1983), although he points out that in

other contexts, a text may be written while a discourse is spoken, a text may not be interactive while a discourse is, a text may be short or long while a discourse implies a certain length, and a text needs to have surface coherence while a discourse needs to have deeper coherence. Lastly, Stubbs points out that other theorists make a distinction between pragmatic realization and abstract theoretical construct; yet, surprisingly, these theorists disagree on which of these is encompassed by the term text. (Hawthorn, 1992).

RESULTS

The essential essence of human speech is the sentence, an unclear construction with infinite variations. It follows that when we construct a sentence, we are moving from the realm of language as a system of signals into the realm of language as a tool for communication, which is expressed through discourse. Discourse theory, discursive psychology, and critical discourse analysis by Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe. The underlying premise of all three strategies is that language plays an active role in both constructing and altering our social relationships, worldviews, and identities rather than passively reflecting them. From the variety of viewpoints within discourse analysis, we have chosen these approaches because we believe they represent especially useful theories and research techniques for studies in communication, culture, and society. They can be used to examine the function of language use in broad societal and cultural trends like globalization and the growth of mass mediated communication, as well as to analyze a wide range of social fields, including organizations and institutions. Michel Foucault's theoretical contributions and practical studies have been crucial in the development of discourse analysis.

DISCUSSION

In nearly every discourse analysis method, Foucault is now a figure to refer to, discuss, alter, and criticize. We will also discuss Foucault, highlighting his contributions to discourse analysis, not just to comply with the unspoken rules of the contest but also because all of our methods have their roots in his theories, even though we reject some of them. Some methods emphasize the necessity for thorough scientific studies of people's written language and spoken language in settings like research interviews and the mass media because they highlight how discourses are formed and altered in everyday discursive activities. Some methods focus more on broad, overarching trends and attempt to map the discourses that are prevalent in society at a certain period or within a particular social area in an abstract manner. Discourse theorists are fully conscious of the structural inequalities that exist between the two sets of texts, but the study of discourse does not distinguish between writings that are classified as literary and those that are classified as non-literary. Autobiographical writings are privileged in their supposed authenticity in relation to an authorial voice;

history texts are entitled in their relationship to truth, for example; and literary texts have a complex relationship to truth and value, being perceived as offering a truth about the human condition but doing so in a fictional and thus “untrue” form. To highlight the similarities these texts exhibit across generic boundaries, it is possible to discuss literary texts alongside other texts, such as histories and autobiographies, and even simpler texts, like recipe books and advice manuals, when discussing the construction, for example, of discourses of femininity and masculinity. Hence, discourse is helpful because it enables us to study textual similarities as the result of a specific set of power and knowledge connections. Discourse theory seeks to comprehend the social as a discursive output from which discourse analytical methods can, in theory, be used to analyze any social phenomenon. We first introduce the discourse theoretical perspective on language, and then we expand the theory to include social areas as a whole. Discourse theory can serve as a theoretical basis for several social constructionist methods to discourse analysis due to its wide scope. Nevertheless, there are not as many useful resources for textually oriented discourse analysis in Laclau and Mo uffe`s writings, as their focus is on theory building. Therefore, it may be beneficial to add techniques from different discourse analysis philosophies to theirs. A broader framework for language and communication is the pedagogical result of this new functional perspective. They now serve as a tool of adaptation and survival in the outside world rather than being characterized as pedagogical goals in and of themselves. One more implication is that, rather than prioritizing grammar above all other adaptation levels, we should consider allocating our teaching resources appropriately if a particular lexical-grammatical structure is offered as one adaptation level alongside others (pronunciation, style, situation, channel, and function). Speaking in a foreign language is frequently equated with engaging in an intercultural communicative exchange, where there is a greater chance of misunderstanding since participants do not hold the same cultural values and language usage norms. Meaning negotiation is even more crucial in this context than it is in intracultural communication. Learners should either diligently study lexicon and syntax under the assumption that they have some contact with natural input, or they should be exposed to the language in authentic situations and with natural frequency in order to achieve an adequate understanding of it. It appears that classroom discourse is the most effective means of organizing the language code that students are expected to learn. Exposure to real-world speech in the target language—provided by the teacher—provides the best opportunity for retaining, expanding, and applying the knowledge of the language. Language serves as both a form of instruction in the mother tongue and the ultimate goal of education, as demonstrated in the case of teaching English to pupils. Having come to the realization that discourse scientists made a concerted effort

to address areas for potential advancement while attempting to characterize the function and significance of language in both contexts at the same time. It has also been established that interaction, both verbal and written, is crucial for language learning efficiency. Language acquisition is further supported by students' communication errors, which lead to meaning negotiation, explanation requests, or message reorganization. Discourse analysts' main concerns have been how students should participate in the learning process, how to manage turn-taking, how to give feedback, and how to teach various skills in the most effective way possible based on discourse analysis offering conversation, each speaker links his or her statement to what has been said before.

CONCLUSION

Discourse analysis has expanded to cover a far wider range of themes in recent years, evolving with linguistic study. These topics include spoken and written discourse, official and informal rhetoric, and the use of language in public and private settings. Discourse analysis and rhetoric analysis, according to K. Eisenhart and B. Johnston, share comparable objectives since they enable text analysis from the perspective of a situational semantic field and take into consideration the mass, characteristics such as culture and even the manner in which content is conveyed. Thus, using discourse analysis in the classroom gives teachers a chance to encourage independent learning and the growth of critical thinking skills, which are essential for lifelong learning overall as well as for all academic subjects.

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